

Optimizing Thermomechanical Properties of Investment Casting Shell Molds

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Abstract

High pressure turbine blades, placed after the combustor on aircraft engines, can present irreparable defects caused by the shell mold at casting. During cooling, a great difference in thermal expansion between the ceramic shell mold and the metal can induce stresses in the blade right after solidification, which could result in discarding defects. Two types of layered alumino-silicate molds (1 and 2), used for non-ferrous casting, were studied.

To determine their thermomechanical behavior, all tests followed a thermal path that mimicked the industrial process, with a dwell at casting temperature (1550°C). Type 2 samples showed higher thermal expansion coefficient rates. Both specimens expanded linearly during the temperature dwell, caused by matrix and stucco interactions, which promote secondary mullitization. Type 2 shells, with higher pore volume fractions, exhibited lower overall Young's modulus values (compared to type 1), while maintaining rigidity at casting temperature. In conclusion, type 2 shells resulted more adequate for investment casting of high-pressure turbine blades.

1. Introduction

Jet engines consist of several different lines of turbomachinery. Turbine blade rows are of the highest importance since many engine parameters, such as fuel savings and thrust, heavily depend on the operating conditions that can be supported by them. Subjected to extreme conditions, blades are fabricated to achieve optimal creep and fatigue resistant behavior ¹.

Equiaxed structures, where many grains are oriented randomly, are more likely to suffer early failure and low work lives. To improve this condition specialized casting methods were introduced, such as directional solidification and seeding, in order to assure a monocrystalline microstructure (eliminating all grain boundaries) ².

The use of single crystal (SX) high pressure turbine blades and vanes made of nickel-based superalloys contributes efficiently to the continuous performance increase of these engines in terms of power and thermal efficiency ¹.

Naturally, this progression has promoted a constant optimization of components in investment casting shell molds to cope with new industrial

demands, as shells are progressively required to endure higher temperatures for longer periods while also being submitted to high thermal gradients.

Until the last decade, zircon was one of the most used materials for shell molds (as flour and stucco) in the investment casting industry due to its high refractoriness and non-reactive nature. However, a sudden increase in the price of this material, in addition to radioactive components (thorium and uranium traces), led to zircon being replaced by diverse alumino-silicates ³.

2. Sample preparation

2.1 Shell construction

Investment or "lost-wax" casting is a technique that allows the production of complex metallic structures. When submitted through a directional cooling gradient (Bridgman furnace), and with the addition of grain selectors, it is possible to control the final microstructure of the piece ¹.

Wax models are covered in alumino-silicate materials (slurry and stucco) to form multilayered ceramic shell molds. Wax is removed at 200°C to render molds hollow before sintering (1100 - 1200°C). Molten superalloys are poured in pre-sintered molds between 1500 - 1600 °C. Finally, molds are broken and removed after cooling to collect the metallic cluster of blades, which will be machined to obtain individual pieces (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the investment casting process, used for manufacturing high pressure turbine blades.

2.2 Studied shell compositions

Each layer of the shell has a particular function as well as a composition of slurry and stucco. Two main zones can be identified: contact and reinforcement.

The contact layer is, as its name suggests, in direct contact with the alloy. It is composed by a ceramic slurry that forms a dense layer which prevents infiltration and ensures a high-quality surface of the solidified blade. It also needs to be chemically inert with the molten metal in order to prevent inclusions and intermetallic phases.

The reinforcement layers are the thickest section of the shell, they are responsible for the thermomechanical properties of the system and are often referred as the skeleton of the shell. Composed by various layers of slurry and stucco, it is in this zone that new components are introduced to optimize the thermomechanical behavior of investment casting shells.

This study evaluated the feasibility of two types of shells, which employed the same alumino-silicate slurries for contact and reinforcement zones but with variations of stucco: 1) dense mullite sand and 2) a mixture of dense and hollow mullite (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of a transversal section of investment casting shell mold Types 1 and 2.

3. Characterization techniques and parameters

3.1 Dilatometry

Dilatometry was performed on a DIL-402 NETZCH apparatus.

Fig. 3 Thermal expansion coefficient as a function of temperature for the alloys: CMSX4, CMSX10, CM186LC, IN738LC and Rene 80⁴⁾.

During cooling, higher thermal expansion rates are favorable in order to minimize induced stress in high pressure blades (as close as possible to those of the alloy = $15 - 16 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, Fig. 3), which are caused

by the difference in thermal expansion coefficient between ceramic and metal (approx. 90%).

3.2 X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Rietveld refinement

Shell samples were analyzed as received (pre-sintered at 1100 – 1200 °C) and after heat treatment stages. These consisted of a 5 °C per minute ramp and one-hour dwells at 1300 °C, 1400 °C, 1500 °C and 1600 °C. All diffractograms were obtained with BRUKER D8 K-Alpha-1, 1D Lynxeye detector and Cu K-alpha-1 source (1.5406 Å). Step size of 0.0197° per second was employed, with rotation of 10 RPM, during 5 hours. All measurements were performed between 10° and 90°.

Rietveld refinement allows quantification of phases by the analytical fitting of XRD data⁵⁾. All analyses were performed on TOPAS – BRUKER, with weighted-profile R-factors (Rwp) < 12%⁶⁾⁷⁾.

3.2 Ultrasonic long bar echography (US-HT)

This technique can be used to study the evolution of elastic moduli of materials at high temperature. Fig. 4 shows that this device consists of a magnetostrictive transducer linked to an alumina wave-guide emits an ultrasonic wave; this tension-compression ultrasound wave is transmitted to the sample in a furnace through the wave-guide⁸⁾.

Fig. 4 Schematics of the ultrasonic long bar technique at high temperature.

The response of the material is received by the transducer and sent to the computer, along with the temperature given by the thermocouple. Young's modulus is calculated as follows:

$$V = 2 \cdot L \cdot \tau^{-1} \quad (1)$$

$$E = \rho \cdot V^2 \quad (2)$$

Where L is the length of the sample, τ the frequency, V the longitudinal ultrasonic velocity, ρ the density of the sample and E the elastic modulus.

Fig. 5 shows typical elastic modulus evolutions for thermally damaged and non-damaged refractories. Non-damageable materials, such as dense α -alumina, exhibit reversible decrease of mechanical resistance as temperature increases, while thermally damaged ceramics experience microcracking closure and subsequent propagation as temperature increases and decreases, respectively.

Fig. 5 Young's moduli evolution with temperature for thermally damaged and non-thermally damaged materials.

3.3 Acoustic Emission (AE-HT)

High temperature acoustic emission is based on the record by sensors of acoustic waves induced by energy release phenomena, occurring within the material during external solicitations, which in this case are temperature variations (Fig. 6)⁹⁾.

Fig. 6 Schematics of the acoustic emission technique at high temperature.

When a material is subjected to a stimulus (thermal path), internal localized initiators trigger the release of energy in the form of stress waves, which propagate to the surface as microcracks. The sum of number of bursts recorded by the sensor is correlated with temperature measurements, obtaining a reference of damage evolution (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 Typical evolution obtained with AE-HT for thermally damaged materials.

All thermomechanical tests were performed through a thermal path that resembles casting conditions. It consisted on a 5 °C / min ramp, in heating and cooling, with a one-hour dwell at 1550 °C.

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Thermal expansion variations with temperature

Fig. 8 Dilatation behavior of Type 1 and 2 samples.

In Fig. 8, both curves show a distortion in linearity after 1150 °C (sintering temperature) due to densification and the formation of glassy phases in the material. During the dwell (1550 °C), both samples present an equivalent linear expansion. Swelling could be caused by the formation of intermediary phases between matrix and stucco.

Type 2 shells show higher overall thermal expansion rates compared to Type 1. As discussed in Sec. 3.1, high thermal expansion coefficient values are favorable in investment casting shells when aiming to prevent residual stress in metallic blades as thermal expansion difference of the system is reduced.

Thermal expansion coefficients for both compositions were calculated during cooling:

Table 1 Thermal expansion coefficient (TEC), at cooling, for shell Types 1 and 2.

Sample	TEC ($\cdot 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$)
Type 1	6.9
Type 2	8.1

4.2 Characterization and quantification of crystalline phases

Fig. 9 shows the comparison between diffractograms of Type 1 shells before (1150 °C) and after sintering at casting temperature (1600 °C). The intensity of mullite peaks increases with temperature, while peaks of alumina become less intense and the peak of cristobalite disappears.

Fig. 9 Superposed XRD diffractograms of Type 1 shell samples before and after heat treatment at casting temperature.

In order to quantify this evolution, Rietveld refinement was performed.

Table 2 Evolution of mullite, corundum and cristobalite quantities (% wt.) with temperature in Type 1 shells.

$\frac{\% \text{wt.}}{^\circ\text{C}}$	Mullite	Corundum	Cristobalite
1300	65.8	30.6	2.6
1400	70.5	27.2	1.8
1500	75.2	23.8	0.9
1600	79.9	20.4	0

The information in **Table 2** confirms that mullitization could be the cause of swelling through the dwell as newly formed mullite detaches from the surface of stucco particles. Both shell types showed similar phase evolutions when analyzed by XRD.

4.3 Elastic properties and damage evolution at high temperature

Fig. 10 Young's modulus and cumulative bursts evolution in temperature of shell Types 1 and 2.

Fig. 10 shows that during heating, values of Young's modulus slightly increase until 700°C in both samples. Type 1 shells had an important increase in rigidity up to 1000°C, caused by the closure of microcracks in the structure, this was later followed by module stabilization. This sudden stiffening starts at 1100°C in type 2 shells. From 1300°C, both materials experience a violent weakening, more pronounced in type 1 shells, until casting temperature (1550°C). This behavior is caused by the fusion of glassy phase in the matrix of these composite materials. During cooling and until 1200°C, the material rapidly stiffens, which is again more pronounced in type 1 shells. This is caused by the solidification of the glassy phase and newly formed phases.

For type 1 shells, the Young's modulus slightly increases until 700°C where a violent weakening of the material takes place. This can be attributed to initiation and propagation of microcracking. AE-HT results confirm this behavior, where the count of

cumulative bursts (stress waves) starts at 700°C until 25°C.

The elastic modulus in type 2 samples experienced a mild progressive decrease during cooling, with a slight brink at 900°C. Nevertheless, the evolution of cumulative bursts is much more pronounced, which means that although the material does not experience sudden weakening, microcracking is more acute.

Three critical temperature points were chosen to facilitate comparison between type 1 and 2 shells.

Table 3 Elastic moduli for types 1 and 2 at critical temperatures during cooling in the casting process.

Sample	E_{1550} (GPa)	E_{1000} (GPa)	E_{25} (GPa)
Type 1	23	60	42
Type 2	34	53	40

5. Conclusions

The main goal of this study was to find shell compositions with high rigidity and resistance at casting temperature, that in addition experience weakening during cooling after the alloy solidifies. Furthermore, high TEC values during cooling are favorable when aiming to prevent casting defects.

Following this criteria, type 2 investment casting shells showed: overall higher thermal expansion rates, overall lower Young's modulus values with lower hysteresis while preserving higher rigidity at casting temperature, when compared to type 1 shells. This information allows to conclude that type 2 shells are more optimal for casting high-pressure turbine blades.

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